

WHY WE NEED A TOURISM AND THE POSSIBILITIES OF REMAINING IMPROVED TOURISM CONSTANTLY

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Abstract: At times, it may seem to countries the economic income which comes throughout tourism too little to increase the country's background and this issue can strongly support why tourism service should not be neglected even though sometimes it might bring not a huge benefit. So next theme can be how make progress in field of tourism which whether can be remained improved or it is to reluctant opinion.

Key words: GDP, service, field of tourism, huge source, recreational, inbound and outbound tourism.

ЗАЧЕМ НУЖЕН ТУРИЗМ И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ОСТАВАТЬСЯ ПОСТОЯННО СОВЕРШЕНСТВУЕМЫМ ТУРИЗМОМ

Резюме: Иногда странам может показаться, что экономический доход, получаемый от туризма, слишком мал, чтобы увеличить национальный фонд, и этот вопрос может убедительно подтвердить, почему туристическими услугами не следует пренебрегать, даже если иногда они могут принести не огромную пользу. Так что следующей темой может быть то, как добиться прогресса в области туризма, который можно ли улучшить, или это вызывает недовольство.

Ключевые слова: ВВП, услуга, сфера туризма, колоссальный источник, рекреационный, въездной и выездной туризм.

TURIZM NIMA UCHUN KERAK VA DOIMIY RAVISHDA TAKOMILLASHTIRILGAN TURIZM BO'LIB QOLISH IMKONIYATLARI

Annotatsiya: Ba'zan mamlakatlarga turizmdan olinadigan iqtisodiy daromad milliy fonga qo'shish uchun juda kichikdek tuyulishi mumkin va bu savol turizm xizmatlarini nega e'tiborsiz qoldirmaslik kerakligi haqida kuchli dalil bo'lishi mumkin, hatto ba'zan ular turistik bo'lmasa ham. katta foyda. Demak, keyingi mavzu turizmda qanday qilib taraqqiyotga erishish mumkinligi bo'lishi mumkin, uni yaxshilash mumkinmi yoki bu norozilikka sabab bo'ladimi?

Kalit so'zlar: YaIM, xizmat ko'rsatish, turizm sektori, ulkan manba, rekreatsion, kirish va chiqish turizmi.

INTRODUCTION

The world becomes very competitive in wide range of services in terms of countries and cosmopolitan cities . It seems a bit sceptical opinion when it comes to get a big cash thought tourism especially when we are talking about cosmopolitan cities which make money from other fields but ,in turn, tourism related countries which absolutely rely on tourism to survive that make us take such cities into considiration.

MAIN BODY

The significance of tourism is uncomparable . The tourism divided in to several parts such as recreational (relax and health-caring), business (international cotracts and united factories) and so on. Next step is types of tourism inbound, domestic and outbound. All types of tourism always served as the huge source income of tourism particularly for Aruba, Bahamas, Maldives and Seychellas.

Such countries are mostly based on tourism in GDP and in fact the half island countries are well-noted by their plesant and convival atmosphere and those places are admired by their high-quality tourism servise.

And sadly but admittedly from 2019 till even 2021 we were undergone Covid-19 and which nearly destroyed tourism in over the world.

And just from 2022 countries started to build service of tourism again. Taking into consideration of only that case that being said that tourism service should urgently be given attention. Because trend only improved till whole quarantine.

Let's looking it into more detailed(1) :

The incomes of particular countries and their possible contribution to the cities.

Rank country	con to GDP	con to emoloyment	average con
Aruba	27.64%	29.91%	28.71%
British virgin islands	32.96%	24.03%	28.49%
Maldives	38.92%	15.74%	27.33%
Seychelles	25.74%	25.35%	25.54%
Bahamas	19.23%	26.48%	22.86%
St.Lucia	15.61%	27.30%	21.45%

So first and foremost tourism improves the overall economy of countries and even tourism feeds several countries.

And secondly, it gives a hand find more attractive places out which can be totally pleasant and surprised that can appeal glaze of people.

The next reason is remaining the importance of historical places and handing the history out to the whole world. Main reasons with high possibilities:

Importance of tourism to the tourist:

Enhanced quality life	Taking a holiday can greatly benefit a personal quality of life. While different people have very different ideas of what makes a good holiday
Ability to broaden way of thinking	Travel is known to help broaden a person's way of thinking. Travel introduces you to new experiences, new cultures and new ways of life.
Educational values	The importance of tourism can be attributed to the educational value that it provides. Travellers and tourists

	can learn many things while undertaking a tourist experience, from tasting authentic local dishes to learning about the exotic animals that they may encounter.
Ability to ‘escape’	Tourism provides the opportunity for escapism. Escapism can be good for the mind. It can help you to relax, which in turn often helps you to be more productive in the workplace everyday life.
Rest and relaxation	Rest and relaxation is very important. Taking time out for yourself helps you to be a happier, healthier person.
Enhanced wellbeing	Having the opportunity for rest and relaxation in turn helps to enhance wellbeing.

Key policy priorities include:

Restoring traveller confidence

Supporting tourism businesses to adapt and survive

Promoting domestic tourism and supporting safe return of international tourism

Providing clear information to travellers and businesses, and limiting uncertainty (to the extent possible)

Evolving response measures to maintain capacity in the sector and address gaps in supports

Strengthening co-operation within and between countries

Building more resilient, sustainable tourism.

National level estimates similarly reflect the scale of the impact on tourism, together with the challenges in making predictions in a fast moving and uncertain situation. Quantifying the current and future impacts of the crisis on the tourism sector is challenging, with the crisis exposing shortcomings in tourism statistical information systems, including a lack of robust, comparable and timely data to inform policy and business decisions.

Potential long lasting tourism policy implications: initial country views

Sustainability may become more prominent in tourism choices, due to greater awareness of climate change and adverse impacts of tourism. Natural areas, regional and local destinations are expected to drive the recovery, and shorter travel distances may result in a lower environmental impact of tourism.

Domestic tourism is expected to benefit, as people prefer to stay local and visit destinations within their own country. Domestic tourists are often more price-sensitive and tend to have lower spending patterns.

Traveller confidence has been hit hard by the crisis, and the ongoing uncertainty. This may lead to a decline in demand and tourism consumption that continues well long after the initial shock.

Traveller behavior will be influenced by the evolution of the crisis, as well as longer term consumer trends that are reshaping in the way people travel. This may include the emergence of new niches and market segments, and a greater focus on safety protocols and contactless tourism experiences.

Safety and hygiene have become key factors to select destinations and tourism activities. People are likely to prefer 'private solutions' when travelling, avoiding big gatherings, and prioritising private means of transport, which may have an adverse impact on the environment.

Structural change in tourism supply is expected across the ecosystem. Not all businesses will survive the crisis and capacity in the sector is likely to be reduced for a period, limiting the recovery.

Skills shortages in the tourism sector may be exacerbated, as many jobs are lost and workers will redeploy to different sectors.

Reduced investment will call for active policies to incentivise and restore investment in the tourism sector to maintain the quality of the tourism offer and promote a sustainable recovery.

Digitalisation in tourism services is expected to continue to accelerate, including a higher use of automation, contact-less payments and services, virtual experiences, real-time information provision.

Tourism policy will need to be more reactive and in the long term it will move to more flexible systems, able to adapt faster to changes of policy focus. Crisis management will be a particular area of focus. Safety and health policy issues also(2).

CONCLUSION

The industrial countries particularly develop and developing cities were already admitted by their tourism field and it means tourism should be addressed not just economic business but also it has to be supported as integral part of exchanging national heritages throughout people and the possible future luck of tourism was predicted as a even like a fact.

LITERATURE RESOURCES:

- 1.www.traveldailymedia.com
- 2.www.tourismteacher.com